

Supporting Information

Suitability of Adenosine Derivatives in Improving the Activity and Stability of Cytochrome c Under Stress: Insights into the Effect of Phosphate Group

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Figure S1: FT-IR spectra in the range of 4000-2250 cm^{-1} depicting the interactions between Cyt c and ADN

Table S1: ΔG for ADN of top cluster.

Cluster	Cluster Rank	ΔG
0	0	-5.953028
0	1	-6.0875363
0	2	-6.0875363
0	3	-6.0881042
0	4	-6.0851197
0	5	-5.7149787
0	6	-5.7909856
0	7	-5.7909856

Table S2: ΔG for AMP of top cluster.

Cluster	Cluster Rank	ΔG
0	0	-6.6490045
0	1	-6.6490045
0	2	-6.6490045
0	3	-6.637321
0	4	-6.637321
0	5	-6.5828137
0	6	-6.5828137
0	7	-6.5828137

Table S3: ΔG for AMP of top cluster.

Cluster	Cluster Rank	ΔG
0	0	-7.1507893
0	1	-7.484726
0	2	-7.3119454
0	3	-7.3119454
0	4	-7.3119454
0	5	-7.12421
0	6	-7.12421
0	7	-7.12421
0	8	-7.122752
0	9	-7.122752
0	10	-7.122752
0	11	-7.1423535
0	12	-7.1423535
0	13	-7.210925
0	14	-7.210925
0	15	-7.210925
0	16	-7.210925
0	17	-6.9228106
0	18	-6.9498734
0	19	-6.9498734
0	20	-6.686313
0	21	-6.5180736
0	22	-6.3776817
0	23	-6.3776817

Table S4: ΔG for ATP of top cluster.

Cluster	Cluster Rank	ΔG
0	0	-8.491465
0	1	-8.491465
0	2	-8.491465
0	3	-8.491465
0	4	-8.321471
0	5	-8.02646
0	6	-8.02646
0	7	-8.02646

Table S5. ADN-CytC interactions predicted by PLIP server

Hydrogen Bonds							
Index	Residue	AA	Distance H-A	Distance D-A	Donor Angle	Donor Atom	Acceptor Atom
1	56A	GLY	2.51	3.24	128.73	934 [N6]	445 [O]
2	58A	THR	2.68	3.59	154.88	454 [N]	935 [N7]

Table S6. AMP-CytC interactions predicted by PLIP server

Hydrogen Bonds							
Index	Residue	AA	Distance H-A	Distance D-A	Donor Angle	Donor Atom	Acceptor Atom
1	73A	LYS	3.51	4.07	115.98	616 [NZ]	933 [N4]

Table S7. ADP-CytC interactions predicted by PLIP server

Hydrogen Bonds							
Index	Residue	AA	Distance H-A	Distance D-A	Donor Angle	Donor Atom	Acceptor Atom
1	23A	GLY	2.78	3.7	155.87	188 [N]	943 [O3]
2	24A	GLY	2	2.86	145.55	932 [O3]	195 [O]
3	26A	HIS	2.92	3.43	113.32	205 [N]	939 [O6]
4	38A	ARG	2.62	3.47	144.57	304 [NH1]	931 [N3]
Salt Bridges							
Index	Residue	AA	Distance	Ligand Group	Ligand Atoms		
1	26A	HIS	4.18	Phosphate	923 [P1], 937 [O5], 939 [O6], 941 [O7], 935 [O4]		

Table S8. ATP-CytC interactions predicted by PLIP server

Hydrogen Bonds							
Index	Residue	AA	Distance H-A	Distance D-A	Donor Angle	Donor Atom	Acceptor Atom
1	26A	HIS	1.97	2.96	164.85	389 [N]	1673 [O8]
2	38A	ARG	2.55	3.48	153.86	575 [NH1]	1661 [N3]
3	44A	PRO	2.09	3.05	164.99	1662 [O3]	663 [O]

π -Cation Interactions						
Index	Residue	AA	Distance	Offset	Ligand Group	Ligand Atoms
1	38A	ARG	4.44	0.48	Aromatic	1657[C2], 1658[N2], 1660[C3], 1661[N3], 1663[C4]

Salt Bridges					
Index	Residue	AA	Distance	Ligand Group	Ligand Atoms
1	26A	HIS	4.76	Phosphate	1653 [P2], 1673 [O8], 1675 [O9], 1676 [O10], 1671 [O7]
2	26A	HIS	4.24	Phosphate	1652 [P1], 1665 [O4], 1667 [O5], 1669 [O6], 1671 [O7]
3	26A	HIS	4.19	Phosphate	1651 [P], 1656 [O1], 1665 [O4], 1659 [O2], 1662 [O3]

Figure S9. Far-CD spectra of Cyt c in presence and absence of adenosine derivatives under oxidative stress.